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The Profitability of Agricultural Production Factors in Europe

38.11% has grown on average between 2011 and 2022

The Eurostat measures the profitability of the factors used in agricultural production in Europe. This indicator takes into consideration the income generated in agriculture and used to remunerate the production factors whether they are proper or borrowed from the farms, such as work, capital, land, wages, equipment, and land rentals. The indicator is placed based on 100 in 2010.

Ranking of European countries for profitability of agricultural production factors in Europe in 2022. Bulgaria is in the first place for the value of the profitability of agricultural production factors in Europe with an amount equal to 377.46 units, followed by Latvia with an amount of 223.51 and Slovakia with an amount of 203.66. In the middle of the standings there are Luxembourg with an amount of 147.88, followed by Greece with a value of 145.9 units and Iceland with an amount of 140.17. The Netherlands closes the ranking with an amount of 87.46, followed by Finland with a value of 77.77 and Malta with an amount of 57.62. On average, the value of the profitability of the agricultural production factors in Europe in 2022 was equal to an amount of 150.75, or on average the agricultural factors were paid for an amount of 50% compared to the corresponding value of 2010.

Ranking of European countries for the value of the percentage variation of the profitability of agricultural production factors between 2011 and 2022. Bulgaria is in the first place for the value of the percentage variation of the profitability of agricultural production factors between 2011 and 2022 with a value equal to 226.92% equal to an amount of 262.00 unit, followed by Latvia with an amount of 133.60% equal to an amount of 127.83 units and by Croatia with an amount of 77.19% equal to a value of 73.67 units. In the middle of the standings there are Hungary with an amount of 29.68% equal to an amount of 44.32 units, followed by Iceland with an amount of 28.09% equal to an amount of 30.74 units and from Estonia with a value of 26.04% equal to an amount of 32.36 units. Finland closes the ranking with an amount of -11.26% equal to an amount of -9.87 units, followed by Malta with an amount of -17.80% equal to an amount of -22.97 units and from Malta with an amount of -34.41% equal to a value of -30.23 units. Overall, the value of the productivity of agricultural factors on average for the countries considered grew by 38.11% between 2011 and 2022 or an amount equal to 41.60 units.

Clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Below is a clusterization with K-means algorithm optimized with the silhouette coefficient. Two different Clusters are then identified or:

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- Cluster 1: Hungary, Slovakia, Czech Republic, Bulgaria, Latvia, Poland, Lithuania, Ireland, Iceland, Italy;
- Cluster 2: Sweden, Austria, Belgium, Netherlands, Luxembourg, France, Germany, Finland, Greece, Malta, Norway, Cyprus, Slovenia, Estonia, Denmark, Switzerland, Spain, Croatia, Romania, Portugal.

From the point of view of the median, it is a dominance of Cluster 1 with respect to Cluster 2. From a geographical point of view, it appears that Italy and some countries from Eastern Europe, together with Iceland and Ireland have a value of the profitability of the high agricultural production factors compared to the corresponding values of the countries of central and northern Europe.

Network analysis with the Euclidean distance. A Network Analysis is presented below with the Euclidean distance. Three network structures are identified, two of which are complex and one simplified. There is a complex network structure composed as indicated below or:

- Cyprus has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.89 units, with Norway for an amount of 0.86 units, with Switzerland for an amount of 0.71 units;
- Spain has a connection with Cyprus for an amount of 0.89 units, with Switzerland for an amount of 0.67 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.84 units;
- Switzerland has a connection with Spain for an amount of 0.67 units, with Cyprus for an amount of 0.71 units and with Norway for an amount of 0.98 units;
- Norway has a connection with Cyprus for an amount of 0.86 units, with Spain for an amount of 0.84 units and with Switzerland for a value of 0.98 units.

The following complex network structure is also detected:

- Luxembourg has a connection with France for an amount of 0.66 units and with Sweden for an amount of 0.98 units;
- France has a connection with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.66 units and with Sweden for an amount of 0.74 units;
- Sweden has a connection with France for an amount of 0.74 units and with Luxembourg for an amount of 0.98 units.

In addition, there is a simplified network structure composed of the following report:

- Finland and Malta have a connection for an amount of 0.91 units.

Conclusions. The profitability of agricultural production factors grew on average in the period considered or between 2011 and 2022 for the countries considered. This condition highlights the fact that the European agricultural production system tends to be efficient. The European Union has invested a lot in agriculture. And these investments appear evident in the profitability of agricultural factors. Agriculture and agro-industry can be considered sectors of excellence in the European economy with good margins of remuneration and profit. However, to improve the agricultural sector, it is necessary to invest more in agriculture-industry connections, improve the distribution systems of the products, increase the defense of local brands, and invest in retaining models of the typicality that can guarantee the originality of the products. Finally, it should be emphasized that farms can also grow at a dimensional level, access international markets, earn further sources of income through the organization of the import-export and through the maximization of the contractual positions of derivatives in international financial markets. Access to these strategies requires the investment in human capital and the creation of a management of farms and agro-industrial farms that is open to

dimensional growth, the share price, to derivative contracts and a process of opening and protagonism in the markets international.

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Appendix

C1>C2

